

ANALYSIS OF PROCESSING PARAMETERS ON THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF MANICARIA FABRIC/PLA BIOCOMPOSITE LAMINA BY THE TAGUCHI METHOD.

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ABSTRACT

Mechanical properties of biocomposites are highly influenced by a number of parameters, including fiber type and content; fiber modification by treatments; and processing method. Hence, the main focus of this study was to analyze the effect of processing parameters on the tensile properties of Manicaria fabric/PLA biocomposite lamina using the Taguchi Method.

The processing parameters studied were: fabric type (untreated/treated), processing temperature (high/low), and fiber content (high/low). A L4 orthogonal array was used to set up the experiments. The ultimate strength and the Young's modulus were used as analysis criteria (output). Since the aim of the Taguchi analysis is to predict the best tensile properties, the Signal to Noise ratio (S/N) used was "Larger the Better". Additionally, analysis of means (ANOM) and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to determine the effect of different parameters.

From the experimental design, it was found that the tensile properties of the Manicaria fabric/PLA composite lamina were significantly improved in comparison to neat PLA. Tensile strength and Young's modulus were increased by 86 % and 97%, respectively. Also, results from ANOM and ANOVA analysis indicated that the fiber type parameter showed the highest contribution to the performance of the composite. In addition, the combination of treated fabric, high temperature, and low fiber content were determined as the optimum levels to maximize the tensile strength and modulus properties of the bio-composite lamina.

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the last years, there has been growing interest in the development of bio-composites based on natural fibers and thermoplastic biopolymers, such as poly (lactic acid) (PLA), among others. These materials not only reduce the dependency on petroleum, but also help to manage the world's waste problem [1]. Many advantages has been associated to the use of natural fibers, including low density, low cost, high specific strength, good acoustic insulation, renewability, biodegradability and availability. However, their low compatibility with hydrophobic polymer matrices reduces its use as reinforcement in composites [2]. Then, for the development of PLA bio-composites it is important to understand the main parameters that influence its performance. In the literature it is possible to find that a significant number of publications deal with the optimization of natural fiber reinforced PLA composites. While some of them investigate the type of fiber [3], or the fiber modifications methods to improve fiber/matrix adhesion [4], others study the effect of fiber content [5] or the processing conditions such as pressure, temperature, and holding time on the mechanical properties of bio-composites [6]. While it is usual that most of the works analyze these parameters individually, in this

study all the parameters are integrated in order to yield the optimum bio-composite properties. Therefore, the aim of this paper is to analyze the effect of parameter processing such as fabric type, processing temperature, and fiber content on the tensile properties of a Manicaria fabric/PLA bio-composite lamina using the Taguchi Method.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

A novel natural fabric extracted from the bract of the Manicaria palm (*Manicaria Saccifera* Gaetner) was used as reinforcement in the bio-composite lamina [7]. It is a brown fibrous material constituted of numerous cross-linked fibers, resembling a fabric, which in this study is called Manicaria fabric (MF). In addition, PolyLactic Acid (PLA) manufactured by Nature Works ® was used as polymeric matrix.

2.2 Composite preparation

Composite laminas were produced by compression molding using the film-stacking method. Layers of PLA and Manicaria fabric were piled-up alternately and hot compressed using a conventional molding press (Dake Press, model 44-251). Processing conditions were set according to the values of the variables in the experimental design.

2.3 Tensile test

Tensile tests of rectangular coupons were carried out in accordance to the ASTM D3090 standard using a universal testing machine (Instron model 3367). Before testing, samples were conditioned for at least 24 h at 23°C and 50 % relative humidity. Testing was conducted at a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min with gauge length of 50 mm, using an extensometer device. At least five specimens were tested per experimental run.

2.4 Experimental design

Mechanical properties of bio-composites are highly influenced by a number of parameters. In the present work, the effects of three process parameters on the tensile properties of the bio-composite were studied. The factors studied were: fabric type, processing temperature and fiber content. These factors were set at two levels as shown in Table 1.

The Taguchi method was used to conduct the experimental design. Based on the number of factors and levels, a L4 orthogonal array was used to set up the experiments as shown in Table 2. Using Taguchi's factorial experimental approach only 4 runs were required to determine the factor effects and their optimal values, while with a full factorial experimental design it would require 8 runs. Then, Taguchi method displays advantages in terms of experimental cost and time.

Item	Control factor	Level 1	Level 2
A	Type of fabric	Untreated	Treated
B	Processing temperature	High	Low
C	Fiber content	Low	High

Table1. Control factors and level.

Run	A	B	C
1	1	1	1
2	1	2	2
3	2	1	2
4	2	2	1

Table 2. L4 Orthogonal array.

To determine the optimal parameters settings for maximizing the tensile properties of the bio-composite lamina, the experimental data needs to be transformed into a signal-to noise (S/N) ratio for analysis. Since the aim of the Taguchi analysis is to maximize the tensile strength and Young's modulus (output), the S/N ratio chosen was "larger the better" (LBT), which is calculated as logarithmic transformation of loss function as shown below

$$S/N_{LTB} = -10\log[MSD] = -10\log\left[\frac{1}{n}\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{y_i^2}\right] \quad (1)$$

where *MSD* is the mean square deviation, *n* is the number of observations and *y* is the response data (output).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To determine the effect of parameter processing on the tensile properties of Manicaria fabric/PLA bio-composite lamina, the experimental results are analyzed using: analysis of means (ANOM), signal to noise ratio (S/N), and analysis of variance (ANOVA).

3.1 Tensile test result analysis

Table 3 shows the experimental results using L4 orthogonal array. The mean tensile properties with their corresponding S/N ratio values are presented for each experimental run. The overall mean of both tensile strength and Young's modulus from all experimental runs were 70.40 MPa and 5.12 GPa, respectively. As well, the S/N ratios were 36.48 dB and 13.92 dB, respectively.

Run	A	B	C	Tensile strength (MPa)	S/N Ratio (dB)	Young's Modulus (GPa)	S/N Ratio (dB)
1	1	1	1	63.53	36.03	4.98	13.91
2	1	2	2	40.18	32.05	3.32	10.42
3	2	1	2	81.88	38.21	6.18	15.81
4	2	2	1	96.00	39.63	6.00	15.54

Table 3. Experimental results using L4 orthogonal array.

To analyze the effect of each factor on the tensile properties the analysis of means (ANOM) was performed. This analysis was carried out by calculating the average of the response criteria for each factor level. Figure 1 and Figure 2 show the effect of the three control factors on the tensile strength and Young's modulus, respectively. To determine the best level for each factor, the factor levels means (blue dots) are compared to the overall mean (dotted line) and the highest value from each factor represents the best level. Therefore, level 2 from fabric type (treated fabric), level 1 from processing temperature (high temperature), and level 1 from fiber content (low fiber content) are the best processing conditions to increase the tensile properties of the composite lamina.

From these results it can be seen that the treatment applied to Manicaria fabric showed to be effective. According to previous studies [7], the surface of untreated fabric is covered by lignin, hemicellulose and waxes, and the treatment used in this study was able to remove certain amount of these materials that inhibit a good fiber/matrix bonding. Also, the treatment allows increasing surface roughness, which results in a better fiber-matrix interfacial adhesion and higher stress transfer capacity [8]. On the other hand, high processing temperature helps to achieve better wettability of the fabric in the melted polymer due to lower viscosity of PLA and better flow properties. This behavior predominates when a low content of fiber is used.

Figure 1. Main effect plots for tensile strength (data means).

Figure 2. Main effect plots for Young's modulus (data means).

3.2 S/N ratio analysis

Table 4 and Table 5 present the results of the S/N analysis for both the tensile strength and Young's modulus, respectively. The optimum factor level set points are the ones with the highest S/N ratio. Therefore, the optimum combination of process parameters for maximizing tensile properties is A2, B1 and C1. This result is consistent with the ANOM analysis on the response presented above.

Level	A Type of fabric	B Processing temperature	C Fiber content
1	34.04	37.12	37.83
2	38.92	35.84	35.13
Delta	4.88	1.28	2.70
Rank	1	3	2

Table 4. S/N ratio values for tensile strength.

Level	A Type of fabric	B Processing temperature	C Fiber content
1	12.16	14.86	14.73
2	15.68	12.98	13.11
Delta	3.52	1.88	1.61
Rank	1	2	3

Table 5. S/N ratio values for Young's modulus.

3.3 Analysis of variance

To determine the relative contribution of the processing parameters on the tensile properties of the bio-composite lamina the analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed. Table 6 and 7 show the results of ANOVA for tensile strength and Young's modulus respectively. For both properties, it was found that the highest contribution is from the type of fabric (untreated/treated). However, the contribution order of the other factors was found to be particular for each property. In the case of the tensile strength the contribution order of the factors is: fiber type, fiber content and temperature. Whereas for the Young's modulus the order is: fiber content, temperature and fiber content. From these results it can be seen that the processing temperature contributes more to the Young's modulus due to the fiber/matrix adhesion mechanism. Whilst the fiber content contributes more for the tensile strength due to the stress transfer capacity of the fabric.

Source	DF	SS	MS	F- value	% Contribution
A	1	23.86	23.86	103.98	72.74
B	1	1.63	1.63	7.14	4.99
C	1	7.30	7.30	31.83	22.26
Error (Se)	0	0.23			

Table 6. ANOVA - S/N ratio values for tensile strength.

Source	DF	SS	MS	F- value	% Contribution
A	1	12.35	12.35	77.38	66.86
B	1	3.53	3.53	22.09	19.08
C	1	2.60	2.60	16.27	14.06
Error (Se)	0	0.16			

Table 7. ANOVA - S/N ratio values for Young's modulus.

3.4 Verification experiment.

After identifying the optimal level of the processing parameters, the final step was to predict and to verify the tensile performance of the bio-composite lamina when the optimal combination level of processing parameters is used. To this purpose, MF/PLA bio-composite lamina was manufactured using the optimum parameters: treated fabric (A2), high temperature (B1), and low fiber content (C1); and it was tensile tested. The results of the verification test compared with the predicted values are shown in the Table 8. Good agreement between the predicted and the verification values was found.

Response value		Predicted	Experimental
Tensile strength	Mean (MPa)	100.61	100.98
	S/N (dB)	40.91	40.00
Young's modulus	Mean (GPa)	6.92	6.36
	S/N (dB)	17.42	16.02

Table 8. Verification test results for optimum configuration.

Additionally, the tensile properties of the optimized lamina were compared to the neat PLA, to understand the reinforcement capacity of Manicaria fabric after the optimization process. Figure 3 shows the tensile stress-strain curves for both materials. As shown, the optimized bio-composite displayed superior mechanical properties compared to the neat PLA. The tensile strength and Young's modulus of the optimized composite were significantly higher than the measured in neat PLA by 86% and 97%, respectively. Therefore, the Taguchi approach is an effective method to determine the optimal processing parameters to maximize the tensile properties of the bio-composite, and treated Manicaria fabric is an effective and promising reinforcement for PLA. [1]

Figure 3. Stress-strain curve for MF/PLA optimized lamina and PLA.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The Taguchi method was used as design experimental technique to analyze the effect of processing parameters such as type of fabric, processing temperature and fiber content on the mechanical behavior of MF/PLA bio-composite.

Experimental results showed that the type of fabric (untreated/treated) has the most significant contribution on the performance of the bio-composite. As well, the analysis of means displayed that the optimum combination of process parameters to maximize tensile properties with the smallest effect due to noise is: Treated fabric (A2), high processing temperature (B1) and low fiber content (C1).

Optimized MF/PLA bio-composite lamina with a tensile strength of 100.98 MPa and Young's modulus of 6.36 GPa was developed. These properties were significantly higher than the measured in neat PLA by 86% and 97%, respectively. Therefore, Manicaria fabric is an effective and promising reinforcement for the development of bio-composites.

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